

An overview

Enable, initiate and promote learning

Support identity development and approaches in coping with everyday life

Enable participation, represent interests

Act and interact consciously and responsibly

Organize and manage (projects)

Competent actors in youth work shown on five areas.

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Glossary

Areas and Dimensions: In the aufZAQ Competence Framework, areas and dimensions divide the descriptions of competences according to their content. Each of the five areas is specified by several dimensions.

aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work: The aufZAQ Competence Framework is a tool that makes competencies of persons involved in youth work visible and comparable. The aufZAQ Competence Framework specifies the NQF for youth work.

Competence: This is applied in practice and is characterized by the way in which personal resources are mobilized or used depending on the situation.¹

Descriptions of competences: They describe competent action by qualified persons in youth work.

EQF and NQF: The European Qualifications Framework is defined by the EU and the National Qualifications Framework is defined by an Austrian federal law. With them, qualifications in all areas of education and education providers (universities, schools, teachers,...) become visible and comparable in Austria and Europe.

Learning Results: They express what learners know, understand and are able to do after they have completed a learning process (e.g., a course).

Levels: In the Competence Framework, levels II to VI divide the descriptions of competences according to their level of requirement. The higher the complexity of the requirement for an action, the higher the level. The levels correspond to the respective levels of the NQF.

1 cf. von Spiegel, H. (2013). Methodisches Handeln in der Sozialen Arbeit. 5th Edition. Ernst Reinhardt Verlag, Stuttgart, p. 72.

1. What is the aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work?

This brochure provides an introduction to the aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work. The following describes how the aufZAQ Competence Framework was created, how it is structured and how it can be applied in practice. In addition, the complete structure and exemplary contents are displayed. The full version with the entire content is available on www.kompetenzrahmen.at as PDF and with interactive access.

The starting point for the aufZAQ Competence Framework was that the Federal Government and the Federal States of Austria, as well as the Youth Work Department in South Tyrol, commissioned aufZAQ in 2015 to develop a standard for educational offers for youth work, that is compatible with the Austrian National Qualifications Framework (NQF). aufZAQ had already certified the quality of trainings, that prepare for work with young people. The aufZAQ Competence Framework that was subsequently developed now serves on the one hand as a basis for the certification of courses and on the other hand as a translation tool to the NQF. In 2017, the Conference of the Youth Departments of the Federal States of Austria defined it as a binding standard for the field of youth work in Austria.

aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work, NQF and EQF?

The aufZAQ Competence Framework serves as a translation tool to the National Qualifications Framework in Austria (NQF) for the qualifications of youth work. This makes them visible and comparable in the Austrian educational landscape. The NQF, in turn, makes qualifications transparent across Europe through the European Qualifications Framework (EQF).

The aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work shows how persons act competently in the work with young people. It covers both open youth work and associational youth work. The aufZAQ Competence Framework takes a cross-action perspective. The descriptions of competences take the technical specifications of open and associational youth work equally into account. In addition, there is no distinction between professional and voluntary work. Because competencies relevant to the subject can be used professionally and voluntarily in various fields of activity for youth work in youth organisations.

Goals of the aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work

The aufZAQ Competence Framework...

- visualizes competences of persons involved in youth work, making them comparable.
- clarifies what persons involved in youth work do and which quality standards they follow.
- increases the quality of educational offerings.
- promotes the mutual recognition of educational providers and users of youth work and of related areas, such as school social work and health prevention.

2. How is the aufZAQ Competence Framework structured?

The aufZAQ Competence Framework is divided into five content areas. These describe the **higher-level content** of relevant competences (for example, „organize and manage [projects]“). The individual areas are specified by **dimensions**.

In addition to the content-related division into areas and dimensions, the Competence Framework also distinguishes between five **levels**. These correspond to levels II to VI of the NQF and thus also the EQF. The levels indicate the **degree of requirement** associated with the respective descriptions of competences.

The aufZAQ Competence Framework also contains a total of 498 **descriptions of competences**. These outline how persons that are involved in youth work act competently. Depending on the focus of the content, the respective competence description is found in the most appropriate dimension and according to the complexity of the requirement at the most appropriate level.

Level II describes, according to the NQF, activities under guidance with a certain degree of independence. This is a minimum requirement for responsible work with young people. As the level increases, the activities shown become more demanding. Level III and IV describe independent work with young people in routine situations. Level V and VI represent competent actions that go beyond routine situations.

The following pages show the five areas with all dimensions as an introduction to the aufZAQ Competence Framework. The descriptions of competences are only shown as an example for each area on the basis of one dimension each (the full version is available on www.kompetenzrahmen.at).

Level

II

Work with young people under guidance with some autonomy; Take responsibility for one's own actions; Be responsible for one's own actions, adapting under certain guidance one's own behaviour to common situations and circumstances in a pre-structured framework

Level

III

Work with young people in simple situations autonomously and self-responsibly; Take responsibility for one's own actions consistent to the situation; Independently adapt one's own behaviour to the state and circumstances of common situations in a pre-structured framework

Level

IV

Work autonomously and self-responsibly with young people in changing routine situations; Plan, carry out, and evaluate projects; Independently adapt one's own behaviour to different situations and under varying conditions to the respective state and circumstances

Level

V

Act independently and flexibly in varying and even unpredictable situations
Coordinate and manage projects and/or teams independently
Instruct colleagues in changing assignments
Participate in the professional development of organisational structures and/or educational concepts

Level

VI

Lead complex and comprehensive functional areas and / or projects independently and ultimately responsible; Deal critically and responsibly with actions of colleagues as well as project and working teams; Take responsibility for managing professional development of individuals, teams, organisational structures, and educational concepts or those of a similar nature

Enable, initiate and promote learning

Dimensions

People working in youth work...

Descriptions of competences

Dimensions	Level II	Level III	Level IV	Level V	Level VI
Set educational goals using a participatory approach and support young people in achieving these goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to the implementation of an educational programme. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to the creation and implementation of a diverse educational programme for a long period of time (e.g. for a year), to which young people can contribute their opinions and issues on topics and decisions that concern them. prepare an educational programme for a short period of time (e.g. for a month) based on the educational goals and/or the principles of the organisation and put it into practice. work in a pre-structured framework according to specified educational goals/concepts/action plans (e.g. educational goals, action plan for sustainability, effective up-to-date educational concepts such as "learning by doing", learning through play, discovery learning). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> plan and create a diverse educational programme based on the educational goals and/or principles of the organisation for a longer period of time (e.g. for a year), to which young people can contribute their opinions and issues on topics and decisions that concern them, and put it into practice accordingly. work independently according to educational goals/concepts/action plans. regularly define the educational goals they aim to reach together with the young people and take measures to reach the set goals. observe the learning progress of young people with respect to the educational goals and derive measures for individual assistance. identify dynamics in children's/youth groups that are beneficial/detrimental for achieving the educational goals and use them consciously to achieve these goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> participate in the development of educational goals/concepts/action plans. work out agreements on objectives with the young people/team members and together develop measures for reaching the set goals. observe learning progress in the team or of the team and, together with the team members, derive measures for team development. systematically observe the achievement of the young people's educational goals. use unexpected group-specific dynamics to achieve the educational goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume final responsibility for the development of educational goals/concepts/action plans and make sure they are implemented adequately. take into account basic and current topics of the young people's environment based on specific experiences/results when developing goals/concepts/action plans. observe, recognise and reflect on the learning progress of team members/staff and independently derive conceptual measures for individual assistance. recognise and reflect on the dynamics in the organisation that are beneficial/detrimental for the achievement of the educational goals and use them in their work to achieve the educational goals.
Create settings which promote (self-) educational processes and learning processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use a pre-structured setting in which young people experience community in a positive way and can feel comfortable and safe. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> make sure to provide a setting where young people experience community in a positive way and can feel comfortable and safe. choose settings to discover/experience/learn together. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> make sure to provide a setting that is adapted to the activities and in which young people experience community in a positive way and can feel comfortable and safe. create diverse and inspiring settings (equipment, objectives, course of a programme) to discover/experience/learn together. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> choose and create settings to discover/experience/learn together, also for unexpected situations. choose suitable settings for specific activities with regard to possible resulting requirements (e.g. for workshops, concert projects). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> make sure to provide structural and occasion-related conditions for settings that are adapted to the goals, target group and place. give team members/staff the possibility to make their own experiences, try things out themselves, create things themselves and learn from their own success and failure.
Support (self-)educational processes and create learning processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use pre-structured settings (e.g. room, infrastructure) to discover/experience/learn together. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> create a learning setting that promotes tolerance and is open to all young people, regardless of their reality of life, moral concepts and youth-cultural affiliation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> give young people the possibility to make their own experiences, try things out themselves, create things themselves and learn from their own success and failure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> participate in creating possibilities for the creation of a need-based learning environment (e.g. infrastructure, material). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> create conditions and possibilities for the creation of a need-based learning environment (e.g. infrastructure, material).
Apply suitable methods for successful learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use existing possibilities of creation in the scope of their work (e.g. material). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inform young people about the educational programme of the organisation as well as its content and goals. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> regularly check if the settings they have created promote learning.
Evaluate and further develop learning processes					

Support identity development and coping with everyday life

Dimensions

People working in youth work...

Descriptions of competences

Dimensions	Level II	Level III	Level IV	Level V	Level VI
Support young people in the development of their identity and their personal development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply simple methods (e.g. games) under guidance of team members/people responsible to promote the personal and social development of young people. • raise the young people's awareness for their environment and the people around them. • enter into contact with young people in an active and supportive way. • support team members/people responsible to deal with challenges that arise concerning the development of young people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply simple methods purposefully to promote the personal and social development of young people. • give young people the chance and time to discover/explore their environment and to change it. • support young people in the development of their own world view. • make an open and safe exchange with young people possible. • show an interest for individual strengths of young people and promote their development. • offer young people the possibility to talk and discuss and thereby encourage reflection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply specific methods purposefully (e.g. group-dynamic exercises) to promote the personal and social development of young people. • help young people to get to know their own limits through programmes and conversations. • encourage young people to go to their limits in activities and, where appropriate, push their limits without overwhelming them. • actively include collective action when supporting and promoting the personal development of young people. • appeal to young people by taking into account their manifold personal forms of expression and not only emphasising single aspects. • give young people sufficient opportunity for physical activity to support their physical development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support young people in finding out their strengths and weaknesses, in becoming aware of their feelings and needs and in talking about them. • promote the finding of and confrontation with personal values and standards as well as those of social environments. • give young people self-motivated feedback about how they view their way of life or their attempts to solve problems. • help young people to consciously shape the way they use media and to reflect on it. • lead projects with a focus on the skills and strengths of the individual young people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support young people in coping with the consequences of differentiation, pluralisation and detraditionalisation of society by applying up-to-date educational methods that are based on specialist theories (e.g. about identity development). • apply up-to-date educational concepts and specialist theories to support young people with manifold problems (e.g. difficult family context, low level of education, debt), identity issues, an identity crisis and/or searches for meaning. • include scientifically confirmed knowledge in their professional relationship practice alongside their personal biography.
Allow young people to experience self-efficacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • encourage young people to make use of their individual skills. • inspire young people to try something new. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • make it possible to experience self-efficacy without pressure to perform in a group. • define achievable goals for young people to make success visible and allow for a sense of achievement. • call young people's attention to the necessary boundaries for their actions to live together in a respectful way. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support young people in the development of their skills and interests as well as in expanding their strengths, especially through constructive criticism, encouraging them to formulate qualified feedback for others, encouraging them to practice self-criticism and supporting them in self-reflection. • offer young people adequate freedom which supports and encourages curiosity and allows them to make discoveries about themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enable the experience of self-efficacy within and outside the organisation. • take into account the special skills, interests and needs of young people/team members/staff and thereby promote their trust in themselves and their skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enable different young people, especially those with multi-dimensional problems (e.g. difficult family context, low level of education, debt), to experience self-efficacy through the application of specialist theories.
Promote that young people take responsibility and act independently					
Foster personal recognition and a sense of community					
Support young people in coping with everyday life					

Enable participation, represent interests

Dimensions

People working in youth work...

Descriptions of competences

Act and interact consciously and responsibly

Dimensions

People working in youth work...

Descriptions of competences

Dimensions	Level II	Level III	Level IV	Level V	Level VI
Take responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> take responsibility for one's own actions in pre-structured situations (e.g. in activities planned by experienced team members). get support when they reach their personal limits. discuss difficult situations in working with young people with team members/people responsible. reliably comply with agreements (punctuality, fulfilment of assumed tasks). support young people as well as team members/people responsible in their tasks. identify the need for support in simple situations and actively offer help to team members/people responsible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> take responsibility for young people in activities that take place regularly (e.g. weekly meetings of a children's/youth group, on-site leisure-educational programmes). be considerate of the personal limits of young people (e.g. regarding physical performance) and make sure these are not exceeded (e.g. by assisting them in activities/programmes). work with young people while paying particular attention to relevant legal framework conditions (e.g. children's rights, youth protection regulations, guidelines on equal treatment). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> take responsibility for young people in extensive activities/programmes/projects (e.g. multi-day activities with overnight accommodation). talk about these relevant legal framework conditions with young people (e.g. children's rights, youth protection regulations, guidelines on equal treatment). support team members in their work with young people in a context-dependent and proactive way. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume responsibility in teams. be considerate of the personal limits of team members and make sure they are not exceeded. prepare themselves for meetings, contribute constructively and make decisions responsibly. make decisions in a decision-making process on their own authority and autonomously while involving the team. estimate the effect of their decisions realistically and are considerate of the interests of the concerned parties. prepare future colleagues for the assumption of responsibility (e.g. independent work with young people) by assisting them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume responsibility for staff and necessary decisions in the organisation. be considerate of the personal limits of staff and make sure they are not exceeded. when necessary, make structural decisions (e.g. the distribution of funding to different subsections of the organisation) in the designated committees or alone, provided that they are authorised to do so. encourage suitable people to assume tasks/responsibility within the organisation. sensibly distribute the responsibility for organisational tasks within the organisation/in their field of work.
Use roles consciously and conscientiously	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> are aware of their role and act accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> consciously and adequately deal with proximity and distance to young people in their work. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reflect on the way they work with young people and develop it and themselves further. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> constantly reflect on their role and use it specifically in their work with young people, parents and other actors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuously observe team members/staff in order to take immediate measures in case of excessively occurring stress (e.g. redistribution of resources, reinforcement of health consciousness, burn-out prevention).
Include the different dimensions of diversity in their work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> act as role models for young people by being open-minded, appreciative as well as tolerant and exemplifying democratic, social and solidary commitment. teach careful and sustainable use of nature and available resources through their own behaviour and actions (e.g. food, material). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> exemplify organisation-specific values and principles in all activities with young people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> are willing to engage in compromise and act in a socially responsible manner. take over an adequate role depending on the conversational and group situation and support, lead, guide or participate accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuously reflect on their work to prevent overworking themselves and immediately take measures (e.g. burn-out prevention) in case of risk of exhaustion (e.g. due to excessive stress, excessive readiness to wear oneself out, imbalance between demands and resources). exemplify personal development for young people/team members by exposing themselves to unfamiliar situations and allowing changes to take place. use their effect as a role model consciously (e.g. to broach or problematise the problem of diversity). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop their own pedagogical profile depending on the tasks and functions and act accordingly. expose themselves to different situations at different levels of the organisation and reflect on their experience to develop themselves further. give team members/staff feedback to support their personal and professional development.
Create group/team settings					
Initiate and create group/team processes					
Accompany group/team processes and develop them further.					
Act in a constructive and solution-oriented manner in problem and conflict situations					
Show risk competence					

A full version can be found on www.kompetenzrahmen.at.

Organise and manage (projects)

Dimensions

People working in youth work...

Descriptions of competences

<p>Shape organisational procedures and processes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support team members/people responsible in carrying out activities that take place regularly (e.g. weekly meetings of a children's/youth group, on-site leisure-educational programmes) according to set goals. • prepare activities that take place regularly according to set goals (e.g. time frame and financial framework) alone and/or in the team with the help of experienced team members/people responsible, carry them out and follow up with a debriefing session. • communicate relevant information (e.g. times and dates for programmes) to young people or their parents in a timely and reliable manner. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plan, lead and coordinate organisationally diverse activities/programmes/projects (e.g. on-site leisure-educational programmes, themed events of the organisation) including preparation and follow-up work independently or in the team. • create long-term planning (e.g. annual planning) for different simple activities/programmes and put them into practice. • take young people's needs, issues and expectations concerning content into account when planning, leading and organising activities/programmes. • plan simple projects (e.g. a practice project for a weekend) on a local/regional level without assistance and carry them out. • organise regular meetings (e.g. weekly meetings of a children's/youth group) and related activities/programmes on a long-term basis (e.g. for a year). • take into account the real-life circumstances on the spot (e.g. facilities) when preparing and organising. • react to minor, spontaneously occurring, organisational needs to adjust independently and depending on the situation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plan, lead and coordinate organisationally extensive activities/programmes/projects (e.g. cross-organisational workshops, public cultural events, play festival in the park, networking events, multi-day activities with overnight accommodation) including preparation and follow-up work independently or in the team. • create long-term planning (e.g. annual planning) for different extensive activities/programmes and put it into practice. • take into account the issues of the participants in the planning, leading and organisation. • communicate relevant information to team members in a timely and reliable manner. • specifically involve relevant contact persons (e.g. parents) in activities/programmes/projects. • apply the principles and values of the organisation to their own work in a reflected way. • act target-oriented in different and sometimes very diverse areas of work and make good use of their resources based on priorities. • check compliance with the planning and identify possible needs for action in case the planning has to be redone/updated. • adapt activities/programmes within the organisation to the team's performance limits and the concrete circumstances. • set rules for process procedures within their area of work and make sure they are complied with. • cooperate with other organisations and institutions when necessary. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • carry the final responsibility for the organisational planning, leading and coordination of complex and extensive activities/programmes/projects (e.g. international youth exchange, cross-regional events, cross-sectoral networking events) including preparation and follow-up work independently or in the team. • create long-term planning (e.g. annual planning) for complex and extensive activities/programmes and take care of its structural implementation. • structure the organisational processes using a participatory approach and implement them accordingly (e.g. by systematically involving the interests and issues of young people). • communicate relevant information to the staff and/or committees of the organisation (e.g. board) in a timely and reliable manner. • cooperate with all participants of the organisation (e.g. young people, parents, team members, people responsible for the organisation, financial backers) in long-term activities/programmes/projects. • develop organisational measures while including expert knowledge and experiences as well as information from the target group and their environment. • make sure the relevant legal provisions are complied with in activities/programmes taking place in the framework of the organisation. • check the organisational processes regularly for their effectiveness and efficiency (e.g. through location determination) and, if necessary, adapt the agreed processes and goals. • make sure the organisation works in a structured and well-planned way (e.g. distribution of the working areas). • intervene in individual areas and in the whole organisation in an occasion-related way, when necessary. • create framework conditions for the exchange of information/coordination between the committees within the organisation. • coordinate the collaboration and coordination between decision-makers within the organisation.
<p>Applying suitable methods for successful organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use simple presentation techniques (e.g. flipchart for visualisation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply methods of moderation (e.g. agendas, introductions) and of documentation of results (e.g. write minutes). • apply structuring methods for planning (e.g. time line, representation of the distribution of tasks). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply differentiated methods of presenting, moderating and documentation of results (e.g. participative collection of ideas). • apply differentiated methods for organisational processes (e.g. online tools for project management) purposefully and adequately. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apply complex planning and management tools for organisational processes (e.g. data banks, online communication platforms) systematically and in a way that satisfies the requirements.
<p>Evaluate and further develop organisational procedures and processes</p>				
<p>Fulfil administrative tasks and use financial means responsibly</p>				
<p>Carry out communication and public relations work</p>				
<p>Shape and develop the organisation</p>				

A full version can be found on www.kompetenzrahmen.at.

3. How can the aufZAQ Competence Framework be applied?

In particular, the aufZAQ Competence Framework is part of the aufZAQ certification of training courses (www.aufzaq.at). In order to be certified, the respective curriculum of a course must be described in a learning result-oriented manner. For the aufZAQ certification, it is determined which learning results correspond to which descriptions of competences of the aufZAQ Competence Framework. In this way, educational offers for youth work are translated into the National Qualifications Framework (NQF).

A youth organization wants to have its course certified by aufZAQ. To do this, they must submit a course curriculum with learning outcomes. These describe what the students should know and be able to do at the end of the course. For assignment to the NQF, these learning outcomes must also be proven. When submitted to aufZAQ, the described learning results are assigned to the aufZAQ Competence Framework – that is, they are assigned to individual descriptions of competences. For that, there is an online tool on www.kompetenzrahmen.at. This assignment determines the NQF level the course can apply for.

The aufZAQ Competence Framework also serves as a resource for the new and further development of courses, as well as support in the creation of action descriptions, job profiles, job postings, self-assessment tools for your own competencies and evaluation tools for application procedures.

4. How did the aufZAQ Competence Framework come about?

Practitioners, experts, multipliers and stakeholders from various levels and sub-areas of youth work, as well as related fields, were involved in the development of the aufZAQ Competence Framework. The entire process was scientifically supported by the Austrian Institute for Research on Vocational Training. In addition, exchanges at the European level helped to incorporate the content of existing competence models¹ into the process.

The data for the aufZAQ Competence Framework was collected through several empirical-discursive survey processes, in which practitioners from the field of youth work directly provided information. From the outset, this participation has promoted the acceptance of the aufZAQ Competence Framework in the field of action.

All the associations of young people were able to participate in the development of the descriptions of competences for **the for the work of youth organizations**. The Austrian National Youth Council (BJV in German) accompanied this process by providing contacts to youth organizations and as an advisory expert. First, a questionnaire was prepared for the collection of data together with interested youth organizations. The questionnaire was then sent out to the 52 member organizations of the BJV. The questionnaire asked for the level of requirements of the activity, the type of activity and the description of typical actions in practice. The youth organizations that participated in the process then filled out one questionnaire for each activity profile. Each of the 30 received activity profiles referred to a specific function or role established in practice (e.g. youth leader). aufZAQ grouped the actions described according to the level of requirement and the areas of content. For this purpose, the action descriptions were coded as part of a qualitative content analysis. In the next step, the grouped data was generalized, standardized in language and descriptions of competences were derived from it. These were discussed again with the practitioners in a feedback loop.

For **open youth work**, aufZAQ organized regional workshops in Austria with practitioners of open youth work as well as board members of bOJA (the umbrella organization of open youth work in Austria) At the workshops, a total of 29 people in small groups described typical actions of open youth work based on key questions. As a result, bOJA, in cooperation with the Institute for Educational Sciences of the University of Graz, developed descriptions of competences for open youth work. The basis for these were existing bOJA quality concepts, scientific research results, existing competence models, as well as the action descriptions of the practitioners of open youth work.

In total, more than 2000 actions were identified in the process, which are typical of youth work. The resulting descriptions of competences from the process of youth work in youth organisations and open youth work were merged as a result. In 2016, the first draft was available. At an Austrian-wide conference, around 80 participants from different areas of youth work discussed the present version. Based on this, the basic structure of the aufZAQ Competence Framework and the quality criteria for descriptions of competences were finalized. Following further feedback loops, the aufZAQ Competence Framework was finalized at the beginning of 2017 with a total of 498 descriptions of competences.

¹ among others SALTO-YOUTH (2016): European Training Strategy. A Competence Model for Youth Workers to Work Internationally.

The aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work aims to make competent acting visible. Its focus lies on people involved in youth work. Amongst others, these include specialists in open youth work, youth leaders in youth organizations, outdoor educators and theatre pedagogy.

This brochure intends to provide an overview of the essential contents of the aufZAQ Competence Framework as well as a description of its utilisation and its connection to the Austrian National and European Qualifications Framework. Additionally, it aims to provide information on the framework's origins and development in collaboration with experts and youth work practitioners.

A complete version of the aufZAQ Competence Framework for Youth Work can be found on the website www.kompetenzrahmen.at. Further information is available at www.aufzaq.at.